

CONDITIONS FOR DESIGNING AN IMMERSIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT IN THE METHODOLOGY OF WORKING WITH GIFTED STUDENTS OF FUTURE INFORMATICS TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article investigates the pedagogical and technological conditions for designing an immersive educational environment (VR/AR, 3D modeling) when preparing future informatics teachers to work with gifted students. The model for developing future teachers' digital competence is based on the TPACK and DigComp frameworks. Additionally, the results of the pedagogical experiment were analyzed, and the effectiveness of the immersive environment in improving the methodology for working with gifted students was demonstrated.*

Keywords: *immersive learning environment, gifted students, future computer science teacher, VR, AR, 3D modeling, TPACK, DigComp, digital competence.*

Introduction

In the context of the modern information society, identifying gifted students, developing their intellectual potential, and providing them with in-depth instruction in computer science is one of the strategic tasks of the education system. Gifted students are characterized by high cognitive needs, an unconventional way of thinking, and the ability to quickly master digital technologies. However, traditional teaching methodology does not provide future informatics teachers with sufficient technological and methodological flexibility to effectively interact with this category of students.

As an innovative solution to this problem, there is a need to integrate immersive technologies (VR, AR, 3D modeling, and virtual educational museums) into the educational process. An immersive learning environment (IEL) allows for the visualization of complex, abstract concepts (e.g., algorithm architecture, network technologies, complex data structures) by creating a sense of presence for the student.

An immersive educational environment is a pedagogical and technological system that allows for the full involvement of the student in the learning process, enhancing cognitive activity and developing creative potential. Such environments, created based on VR, AR, artificial intelligence, and gamification elements, are of particular importance in meeting the cognitive needs of gifted students [9].

For future teachers to be able to design such an environment for gifted students, they themselves must possess a high level of digital competencies [4]. It is advisable to organize this process based on internationally recognized TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) and DigComp (Digital Competence Framework) models.

At the same time, pedagogical science and educational practice have insufficiently studied the issue of preparing future informatics teachers for designing and effectively using such

environments. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" [2] and the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy [1] define the digitalization of education and support for talented youth as priority tasks.

The purpose of this research is to identify and scientifically substantiate the pedagogical and technical-technological conditions for designing an immersive educational environment in the methodology of future informatics teachers' work with gifted students.

Literature review

The term "Immersive Education" was originally used in military simulations and medical education and later entered the field of general education [7]. In modern literature, this concept refers to the complete immersion of the student in the learning process involving all their senses [6].

The main types of immersive environments are the following: 1) Virtual Reality (VR) - a technology that fully "dives" the student into an artificially created digital world; 2) Augmented Reality (AR) - a technology that adds digital elements to a real environment; 3) Mixed Reality (MR) - a technology that combines two environments; and 4) 360VR video and simulation environments - technologies that provide educational content in an interactive manner [5].

R. Atamuratov characterizes immersive learning as an innovative pedagogical approach that allows for the creation of complex experiences in a virtual environment that are impossible to implement in traditional classroom settings [3]. K. Patil notes that immersive learning based on virtual reality serves to develop students' empathy, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills [11]. E. Uzcan and his team describe the immersive learning environment as a digital educational ecosystem created based on virtual reality technologies and supporting students' cognitive, emotional, and social activity [10]. J. Lin emphasizes that an immersive environment is a technology that allows students to visualize abstract concepts and model complex processes [8]. According to Y. Wang and Z. Wang, an immersive learning environment, increases students' motivation, helps retain knowledge in long-term memory, and supports experiential learning [12]. A meta-analysis of 69 studies conducted by Merchant and colleagues proved that simulation games and virtual environments have a positive impact on educational outcomes [9].

The analysis of the aforementioned scientific views shows that while immersive learning is an innovative pedagogical approach that transforms the student into an active subject of the educational process, the immersive educational environment is a technological and pedagogical space that serves to implement this approach. As a result, it is possible to develop students' motivation, practical skills, and creative and critical thinking.

Research methodology

The study utilized a systems approach, pedagogical modeling, comparative analysis, and pedagogical experimental methods. The methodology for designing an immersive learning environment is based on the following conceptual frameworks:

1) TPACK model. The future teacher's knowledge of the subject (content), pedagogical skills (pedagogy), and the ability to synthesize immersive technologies (technology).

2) DigComp framework. Competencies in digital content creation, security, and problem-solving in the digital environment.

Pedagogical experimental work was organized at the centers of pedagogical excellence in the Samarkand and Kashkadarya regions. A total of 354 students (computer science teachers) participated in the experiment. The students were divided into two groups (experimental and control). The control group (175 people) was trained using traditional methods and standard

electronic educational resources. The experimental group (179 people) was trained in a specially designed immersive learning environment (VR laboratories, 3D visualization modules, and virtual engineering case studies).

The level of students' methodological readiness for working with gifted students was assessed based on three criteria (motivational-targeted, cognitive-content, technological-activity) on a 100-point scale.

Results

The results obtained at the end of the pedagogical experiment showed a significant increase in the experimental group compared to the control group. The indicators of future teachers who studied in an immersive learning environment while adhering to design conditions are reflected in the following table (Table 1):

Table 1. Dynamics of the level of methodological training for future teachers

Groups	Number of participants	Low level (%)	Medium level (%)	High level (%)	Average score (on a 100-point scale)
Control group	175	32,5%	48,0%	19,5%	64,2
Experimental group	179	8,4%	44,1%	47,5%	82,7

The share of high-level listeners in the experimental group increased by 28% compared to the control group, while the average score increased from 64.2 to 82.7 (+18.5 points) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Comparison of the results of the experimental and control groups

When checking the reliability of the results obtained using mathematical and statistical methods (Student's t-test), it was proven that the difference between the groups is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This directly confirms the effectiveness of the immersive environment components.

Discussion. The results obtained show that the successful design of an immersive learning environment in the methodology of future computer science teachers working with gifted students depends on three main conditions:

1. Pedagogical and methodological conditions (TPACK integration). Immersive technologies should be not just a visual tool but a means of stimulating the research activity of a gifted student. A future teacher must be able to formulate "divergent thinking" tasks for a gifted student in a VR/AR environment (finding multiple solutions to the same problem). In our model, the lesson scenarios developed based on TPACK helped the future teacher uncover the most complex sections of the subject within the technology (for example, the visualization of artificial intelligence neural networks).

2. Technical and technological conditions (DigComp and level of immersiveness). An immersive learning environment must possess a high level of interactivity and an "immersion" indicator. To achieve this, future teachers were trained to create elementary 3D models on Blender, Unity, or Unreal Engine platforms and integrate them into the lesson. According to the DigComp framework, the teacher has moved from consuming ready-made digital content to creating its architecture. This will allow you to work on startups and projects together with talented students.

3. Psychological and didactic conditions (creativity and motivation). Gifted students quickly get bored with standard schemes. The immersive environment gives them the freedom not to be afraid of making mistakes and to conduct unlimited experiments in virtual laboratories. Since the future teachers in the experimental group mastered this specific didactic pattern, the results demonstrated by their students were high.

The results of this study align with international experience in applying immersive technologies in education and enrich the local methodological base for digitalizing the teacher training system.

In the future, in the process of training future informatics teachers, it is important to widely implement immersive learning environments, integrate VR/AR and artificial intelligence technologies, improve methodological support for working with gifted students, and develop criteria for assessing immersive pedagogical competence. Furthermore, conducting large-scale experimental research in various educational institutions and creating a national database of digital educational resources will serve to further develop the scientific and methodological foundations of this field.

Conclusion. Improving the methodology for future informatics teachers to work with gifted students through an immersive learning environment is an urgent pedagogical need of today. Ensuring the synergistic integration of TPACK and DigComp models in the design of an immersive educational environment and training future teachers not only as VR/AR users but also as its pedagogical designers is the main factor guaranteeing the quality of education.

Based on the research results, the following practical recommendations were developed:

1. It is necessary to introduce the "Immersive Educational Technologies" module for future computer science teachers in higher education institutions and to focus on forming immersive environment competencies in their professional development programmes;

2. In educational practice, it is advisable to emphasise the teaching of differentiated methodologies for working with gifted students and to establish a mentoring system and practical laboratories between general education schools and higher education institutions.

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